

The effect of zinc nanoparticles inhibitor of efflux pumps NorA and NorB in clinical isolated of Staphylococcus aureus from skin infections

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Abstract

Background and Aim: The escalation of antibiotic resistance attributable to the extensive application of antibiotics stands as a primary contributor to the ineffectiveness of antibiotic treatment. Leveraging synthetic nanoparticles endowed with antimicrobial properties either individually or in conjunction with antibiotics presents a promising approach. Among the pivotal resistance mechanisms in *S. aureus* are efflux pumps, notably NorA and NorB, which exhibit resilience against fluoroquinolone antibiotics. This investigation aimed to assess the efficacy of zinc nanoparticles in regulating NorA and NorB efflux pumps in clinical strains of ciprofloxacin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from cutaneous infections in Qom.

Materials and Methods: Skin infection samples were procured from hospitals and local clinics over a span of five months (August 2017 to December 2017). *S. aureus* isolates were identified from the skin infection specimens utilizing standard biochemical methods and culture. Subsequent to confirmation of the presence of *femA* and *nuc* genes via Multiplex PCR, indicative of *S. aureus* molecular detection, ciprofloxacin-resistant isolates with active efflux pumps were discerned employing disk diffusion tests, MIC CP, MIC zinc nanoparticles, Cartwheel Method, and phenotype analyses with the aid of a pump inhibitor combination (CCCP) alongside ciprofloxacin. PCR assays were conducted to confirm the presence of *norA* and *norB* genes as targets, along with the *16srRNA* and *jmK* housekeeping genes. Lastly, Real-Time PCR was employed to assess the expression levels of *norA* and *norB* genes and the impact of zinc nanoparticles thereon.

Results: Among 230 clinical samples, 90 isolates were identified as *S. aureus* through standard biochemical and culture techniques. Multiplex PCR revealed *femA* and *nuc* genes in 88 isolates. Notably, 50 isolates (56%) exhibited resistance to fluoroquinolones based on antibiotic susceptibility patterns. From these, 12 isolates displaying active efflux pump phenotypes were selected. Real-time PCR results indicated varying degrees of upregulation in the expression of *norA* and *norB* genes in response to ciprofloxacin, with fold changes of 1.5 and 2.3 respectively, while zinc nanoparticles exhibited fold changes of 1.6 and 0.8 respectively. When subjected to sub-MIC CP with ZnNP, fold changes of 1.4 and 0.4 were observed.

Conclusion: This study underscores the potential of zinc nanoparticles in conjunction with ciprofloxacin to mitigate the expression of pump genes associated with fluoroquinolone resistance.

Keywords: Staphylococcus aureus, efflux pumps, norA, norB, zinc nanoparticles, fluoroquinolones.

1. INTRODUCTION

A class of Gram-positive bacteria with a diameter of 0.5 to 1.5 μm is known as staphylococci. Their unique morphology is defined by individual cocci that divide into several dimensions to form cluster arrangements that have a grape-like appearance. There are 32 species and 8 subspecies in the *Staphylococcus* genus, most of which are found on human tissue. Among the strains in this genus, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermis* are particularly well-researched (1, 2).

One notable causative agent of infections acquired in both hospitals and the community is *Staphylococcus aureus*. It is becoming a major global health problem because of its increasing pathogenicity and resistance to antimicrobial treatments. With the use of a wide range of toxins, direct invasion methods, and clinical manifestations, this bacterium demonstrates an amazing ability to cause a wide range of diseases (3-5). Three primary categories comprise the range of infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*: (i) superficial diseases like wound infections; (ii) toxin-mediated illnesses such as food poisoning and skin peeling syndromes; and

(iii) systemic and potentially fatal diseases like endocarditis, osteomyelitis, pneumonia, brain abscesses, meningitis, and bacteremia (6). Pathogenicity is largely dependent on a variety of virulence factors that *Staphylococcus aureus* possesses, including both structural and secretory products. These comprise, among others, eight enterotoxins, a toxic shock syndrome toxin, exfoliative toxins A and B, and at least five cytolytic or membrane-disrupting toxins (alpha, beta, delta, gamma, and Panton-Valentine leukocidin) (7).

The most common type of *Staphylococcus aureus* infection is skin and soft tissue infection, which can involve deeper structures like soft tissue abscesses or superficial involvement of the upper skin layers (e.g., cellulitis). *Staphylococcus aureus* is frequently responsible for bone and joint infections, such as acute osteomyelitis and septic arthritis. Normal heart valves are frequently affected by staphylococcal endocarditis, which usually presents as acute bacterial endocarditis (7, 8).

The fast evolution of resistant bacteria has led to a substantial threat of bacterial infections reemerging despite decades of use of antibiotics since their invention. The overuse of antibiotics and the lack of innovative medication research initiatives are the root causes of this dilemma. Antibiotics, which have revolutionized medical practice and saved countless lives throughout history, are at risk due to the widespread rise of antibiotic-resistant bacteria (9-11).

Researchers found that various resistance efflux systems were common in microorganisms in the late 1980s. A class of tetracycline efflux pumps, which cause widespread resistance to tetracycline antibiotics in both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, was among the first drug transport proteins discovered in bacteria. As of right now, prokaryotes have been found to harbor five families of these pumps, which contribute to antibiotic resistance in general (12-14). Because they actively remove drug compounds from the cell, efflux pumps are essential in the development of multidrug resistance because they decrease the permeability of the membrane to these compounds (15).

In addition to excreting different types of quinolones (such as norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin, which are hydrophilic, and moxifloxacin and sparfloxacin, which are hydrophobic), Nor family pumps can also excrete other chemical compounds such as bromide, cetrимide, and tetraphenylphosphonium (16).

Researchers in the field of nanotechnology are becoming increasingly interested in treatments based on nanotechnology, with the hope that breakthroughs in nanoscience may transform the battle against various illnesses like cancer and atherosclerosis. Nanomaterials, molecular nanotechnology, and biotechnology are the three main subfields of nanotechnology that show promise for important discoveries and advances in modern medicine (17).

It is believed that zinc oxide nanoparticles are biocompatible and non-toxic. They have proven useful as delivery systems for cosmetics, medications, and medical fillers (18, 19). Zinc oxide nanoparticles have been shown in recent studies to possess antibacterial activities against foodborne pathogens, including enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* and *E. Coli* O157:H7 (2, 19, 20).

2. MATERIAL AND METODS

This study examines how zinc nanoparticles, which are known to have antimicrobial properties, affect efflux pumps that are linked to resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria.

Study population

The population of this study includes all strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*). 230 samples were obtained from suspected *S. aureus* samples referring to Nekoi-Hedayati, and Aliebne Abitaleh hospitals in Qom City from September 2018 until February 2019. They were collected and sent to the research laboratory of Islamic Azad University, Qom branch.

Sample collection

Sample collection was taken using sterile swabs after cleaning the wound surface from the deep parts of the wound and immediately put into tubes containing BHI Broth (Merck, Germany) and sent to the laboratory within 4-6 hours. After that, the tubes were incubated overnight at 37°C. Next, one loop was removed from the medium and cultured as four-stage culture on BHI agar medium (Merck, Germany).

Phenotypic detection and identification tests

To determine the identity of *S. aureus*, the following tests were used. Gram staining to observe the morphology of bacteria, catalase test, slide, and tubular coagulase, growth on Mannitol Salt agar, growth on blood Agar medium, DNase test, PCR test to determine *femA*, and *nuc* gene to confirm *S. aureus* species. All tests were performed according to CLSI guidelines 2019.

Storage of isolated colonies

For storage of isolated colonies, the bacterial colony was cultured in BHI Broth medium and after growth, a cell sediment of it was prepared. After preparing the cell sediment, 18% glycerol was added to the BHI Broth medium and mixed well. In the end, the lid of the tubes contains the mix was secured with parafilm and placed in a -20 freezer for about 5 days. After that, the tubes were transferred to the -70 freezer.

Evaluation of antibiotic sensitivity

To determine the antibiotic susceptibility of isolates, antibiotic discs were utilized. The discs include; Ciprofloxacin, Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Levofloxacin, and Polymyxin B (Padtanteb, Iran). To perform the antibiogram, first, a concentration of 0.5 McFarland was prepared from the bacteria and OD 620 nm was used to evaluate the 0.5 McFarland mixture.

Mueller Hinton-Agar medium (Merck, Germany) was prepared according to the instruction of CLSI. After 18-24 hours of the culture of bacteria which are grown in the blood agar medium, a suspension with a turbidity equal to 0.5 McFarland's concentration was prepared. Then this suspension was inoculated with a sterile swab on Muller Hinton agar medium in three different directions and after a few minutes, antibiotic discs were placed on the medium at distance of 22 mm from each other and 16 mm from the wall of the plate. After that, it was heated at 35°C and then the diameter of the halo of non-growth was measured after 16-20 hours for all antibiotics. A diameter of 15 mm and less was considered resistant, a diameter of 16 to 20 mm was intermediate, and a diameter of 21 mm and more was considered sensitive. The standard strain of *S.*

aureus ATCC 25923 was used to control the tests of determine the sensitivity to antibiotics.

Phenotypic investigation of the efflux pump

Cartwheel method was used for phenotypic investigation of the presence of an efflux pump in isolated colonies. For each of the resistant bacteria, a semi-McFarland was made. After making the TSA medium, ethidium bromide stock was prepared at a concentration of 1 gram/ml. Then 5 different concentrations of ethidium bromide including; 0,250,500,750,1000 µL were added to the TSA medium whose temperature had reached 40°C. After 24 hours and ensuring that the plates were not contaminated, each resistant bacteria was cultured on 5 plates with different concentrations of ethidium bromide. The results were checked using the gel dock. The standard strain of *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 was used to control Cartwheel.

Synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles

Zinc acetate and oxalic acid (Merck, Germany) were mixed and rubbed for about an hour. Then it heated at 450°C for one hour. The obtained white powder is zinc nanoparticles, which was used by scanning electron microscope (TEM) spectrophotometry to ensure the presence and characteristics of zinc nanoparticles.

Determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

In this test, variable concentrations of antibiotics are added to the liquid culture medium. For this purpose, ciprofloxacin antibiotic Broth microdilution method was used. In this method, microplates which have 96 small holes was used. These holes are filled with a specific amount of antibiotics, a standard number of bacteria, and a certain amount of culture. The microplates were placed at a temperature of 35-37°C for 18-24 hours. The turbidity of each well was checked. If the first well of each column did not grow, it was

considered as the MIC concentration. A concentration of $4 \geq \mu\text{g/ml}$ was considered resistant, a concentration of $2 \mu\text{g}$ was intermediate, and a concentration of $1 \leq \mu\text{g}$ was considered sensitive.

CCCP (carbonyl cyanide 3-chlorophenylhydrazone) is a chemical inhibitor of the efflux pump and its minimum inhibitory concentration was measured for all strains. A concentration was selected that had no effect on inhibiting the growth of bacteria and it was used along with ciprofloxacin in the MIC method on the strains (Klančnik, Možina, and Zhang 2012).

MIC nano zinc and MIC CP

Using nano zinc powder and distilled water, a stock of nano zinc was prepared which had a concentration equal to 4096 mg/ml. Then, using this stock, the MIC of all 50 resistant isolates was done. In the next step, the MIC of CIP was added to each isolate along with a fixed concentration of nano zinc using a stock of 4096 mg/ml.

Molecular diagnosis tests

DNA extraction was done using the boiling method (Kariuki et al. 2001). After extracting DNA, to check the quality of extracted genomic DNA, the samples were electrophoresed on 0.8% agarose gel. In this study, six pairs of primers were used for *femA*, *nuc*, *norA*, *norB*, *16sRNA*, and *jmK* genes (Table 1). The *femA* and *nuc* gene were selected for the molecular identification of *S. aureus*, as the identification genes of the strains. *16SRNA* and *JmK* genes were also selected as reference genes, and *norA*, *norB* were selected as target genes. The PCR was performed according to the master mix manufacturer's protocol (CinnaGen, Iran). In the next step, PCR products were electrophoresed on agarose gel. After adjusting the amplification conditions, the multiplex PCR with the standard sample was performed.

Gene	Primers (5'-3')	Size of amplified product (bp)
<i>femA</i>	F-CGA TCC ATA TTT ACC ATA TCA R-ATC ACG CTC TTC GTT TAG TT	450
<i>nuc</i>	F- GCGATTGATGGTGATACGGTT R-AGCCAAGCCTTGACGAACTAAAGC	270
<i>norA</i>	F-TGG TAT GAG TGC TGG TAT GG R-AAC TTC TGC CAT AAA TCC ACC	157
<i>norB</i>	F-ATGATTCGTGTWGGTGAAAA R-CATTTTATAGATACCTGMAGC	258
<i>16sRNA</i>	F-ACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG R-ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGG	181
<i>jmK</i>	F-TCAGGACCATCTGGAGTAGGTAAG R-TTCACGCATTTGACGTGTTG	108

Table1. primer sequences used in this study

Before RNA extraction, a single bacterial colony was inoculated in a tube containing BHI broth medium and mixed well. Then the tube was vortexed and placed in a shaker incubator at 37°C. These tubes are used for RNA extraction as a pre-culture.

After 18-20 hours next to the flame, about 100 microliters of the overnight culture was added first to a tube containing sterile BHI broth medium and then to other tubes containing sterile BHI broth medium with a sub-MIC concentration of the antibiotic ciprofloxacin strain, zinc nanoparticles, and Sub MIC of zinc nanoparticles along with ciprofloxacin was added and

every six tubes after 1-4 hours were prepared for RNA extraction. This process was done by the extraction kit of CinnaGen company according to the manufacturer's protocol. After preparing the RNA, cDNA was made using the 2-step RT-PCR Kit (Vivantis, Malaysia) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The Real-time PCR reaction was performed by SybrGreen (CinnaGen, Iran) using specific primers for each gene. Real-time PCR was done on 12 resistant isolates before and after ciprofloxacin antibiotic, and zinc nanoparticles with ciprofloxacin and a standard strain of *S. aureus*.

In the end, using REST 2009 software, the data obtained from Real-time PCR reaction and changes in expression of norA, and norB genes compared to 16sRNA, and JmK were analyzed in the presence of different dilutions.

3. RESULTS

Sample collection and bacteria identification result

Among the 230 collected samples, 150 men samples (65.21%) and 80 women samples (34.78%), the number of 90 (39.13%) isolates including 64 men isolates (42.66%) and 26 women (32.5%) isolates were diagnosed by biochemical methods and *S. aureus* culture. The number of 88 isolates

was confirmed by molecular methods and included in the research. All gram-positive, catalase-positive, coagulase-positive, and DNase-positive strains that had beta hemolysis on the medium and also had femA and nuc genes were considered *S. aureus*.

Phenotypic test result

The phenotypic evaluation of resistance to antibiotics was investigated by the phenotypic agar disk diffusion method and the antibiotic sensitivity determination pattern of 88 isolates which the details are given in Table 2. Figure 1 shows the antibiotic-resistant and antibiotic-sensitive strains.

Antibiotic disc	The number of susceptible isolates (%)	Number of intermediate isolates (%)	Number of resistant isolates (%)
Ciprofloxacin 5µg	38 (43.18%)	-	50 (56.81%)
Ofloxacin 5µg	37 (42.04%)	1 (1.13%)	50 (56.81%)
Norfloxacin 10µg	38 (43.18%)	-	50 (56.81%)
Levofloxacin 5µg	37 (42.04%)	1 (1.13%)	50 (56.81%)
Polymyxin B	-	-	88 (100%)

Table2. The degree of sensitivity to different antibiotics in the strains of *S. aureus*

Figure1. Antibiogram test on plate

A: resistant sample

B: sensitive sample

Antibiotic resistance tests result

After conducting antibiogram tests for 88 isolated *S. aureus*, the frequency distribution of their drug resistance pattern compared to the fluoroquinolone family was investigated. Among them, the number of 50 isolates (56.81%) were resistant to the fluoroquinolone family and the number of 38 isolates (43.18%) were sensitive to the fluoroquinolone family. Among the resistant isolates, 18 isolates (36%) were associated with women's skin ulcers, and 32 isolates (64%) were associated with men's skin ulcers. Also, among the sensitive isolates, 15 isolates (39.47%) were associated with

women's skin ulcers, and 23 isolates (60.52%) were associated with men's skin ulcers.

Dispersion of zinc nanoparticles and electron microscope results

The dynamic light scattering (DLS) method is used to measure the size of nanoparticles in the liquid medium. The dispersion of nanoparticles was obtained according to Figure 2, and about 24% of the size of the zinc nanoparticles in the solution was 10 nm, which was the largest percentage in terms of size. Figure 3 represents the result of the electron microscope.

Figure 2. Dispersion of zinc nanoparticles in percentage

Figure3. Electron microscope image of zinc nanoparticles

Cartwheel test results

Cardwell test was done for all resistant bacteria. Among them, the number of 18 isolates were dark inside the gel duct after exposure to UV light. In other words, 18 isolates have an active efflux pump that was able to remove the ethidium bromide

dye, which created dark colonies after exposure to UV light (Figure 4).

Figure1. The results of the PCR reaction for the desired genes, the electrophoresis of the PCR product of the *cyIA* gene (Figure E) and the *hyl* genes (Figure F)

Figure 4. Cardwell test result: positive clinical isolate (having an active efflux pump) = dark color; ethidium is released from the cell. Negative clinical isolation (lack of active efflux pump) = white color; accumulation of ethidium bromide inside the cell

MIC CCCP test results

CCCP was applied to all 50 resistant samples, and finally sub-MIC CCCP was observed for all isolates at concentration of 10-20 μ M. To make sure, the concentration of 10 μ M along with Sub MIC CP was considered for resistant isolates. The number of 12 isolated resistant to fluoroquinolones changed in their sub-MIC concentration along with 10 μ M CCCP concentration and had an active pump.

Nano zinc MIC test results

The MIC of nano zinc with stock concentration of 4096 mg/ml was set for all 50 resistant isolates. For each Sub MIC CIP isolate, along with different concentrations of nano zinc, serial dilutions were prepared using 4096 mg/ml stock, and then the MIC of all resistant isolates was set. The result of MIC was shown in table 3. The MIC AU was 600 μ g/ml, and MIC ZN was 1024 μ g/ml for all 50 resistant isolates.

MIC of 50 resistant isolates (μ g/ml)	Number of MIC CP+AU	Number of MIC CP+ZN
8	1 (2%)	1 (2%)
16	2 (4%)	3 (6%)
32	9 (18%)	9 (18%)
64	5 (10%)	5 (10%)
128	20 (40%)	14 (28%)
256	13 (26%)	18 (36%)

Table3. The result of MIC from 50 resistant isolates

Molecular tests results

For all the isolates which were identified as *S. aureus* by phenotypic methods, *femA*, and *nuc* genes were amplified

using specific primers. Among the 90 isolates that were identified as *S. aureus* by phenotypic methods, 88 isolates were confirmed by molecular methods (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Multiplex PCR product electrophoresis of *femA* and *nuc* genes on agarose gel. Column M marker 100 bp (SinaClon Company), column 9 negative control (no DNA), column 10 positive control (25923 ATCC), columns 1 and 2, 4 to 8, 10 to 16, 17 to 21, 23 and 24 positive clinical isolates, row 3 negative clinical isolates, row 22 *femA* positive and *nuc* negative clinical isolates.

Amplification of *norA*, and *norB* genes of all 88 *S. aureus* isolates was done using its specific primers. Because *norA* and *norB* genes are chromosomal genes, the presence of this gene

in the chromosome of *S. aureus* was confirmed. All 88 isolates also had the mentioned genes (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Multiplex PCR product electrophoresis of *norA* and *norB* genes on agarose gel. Column M marker 100 bp (Sina Clone Company), column 3 negative control (no DNA), column 2 positive control (ATCC 25923), column 1 positive clinical isolate.

jmK, and *16sr RNA* genes were considered as reference genes in Real- time PCR. The presence of these genes is certain in the chromosome of *S. aureus*. The presence of these genes was

also evaluated for all the isolates. All 88 *S. aureus* isolates had both *jmK*, and *16sr RNA* genes (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Multiplex PCR product electrophoresis of jmK and 16sr RNA genes on agarose gel. Column M marker 100 bp (SinaClon Company), column 8 negative control (no DNA), column 7 positive control (ATCC 25923), columns 1 to 6 positive clinical isolates.

Real-time PCR was used to quantitatively measure the expression of *norA*, and *norB* genes in 12 strains resistant to fluoroquinolones and a standard strain (ATCC 25923). The efficiency of Real-time PCR reaction for *norA*, *norB*, *jmK*, and 16sr RNA genes was calculated 95%, 96%, 97%, and 94% respectively. *jmK*, and 16sr RNA genes were considered as reference genes.

Real-time PCR result

Real-time PCR was used to quantitatively measure the expression of *norA* and *norB* genes in 12 strains resistant to

fluoroquinolones and one standard strain (ATCC 25923). The results of CT values obtained from the Real-time PCR reaction using REST 2009 software for 12 resistant isolates along with a standard sample (ATCC 25923) before and after exposure to the ciprofloxacin antibiotic were analyzed.

A significant difference was observed between the two bacterial groups before and after exposure to the ciprofloxacin antibiotic. The result was showed, a 1.5-fold increase in *norA* gene expression and a 2.3-fold increase in *norB* gene expression (Figure 8).

Figure 8. The result of 12 strains resistant to fluoroquinolones, before and after exposure to the ciprofloxacin antibiotic Also, the results of the analysis of Real-time PCR before and after exposure to nano zinc were analyzed which represented a significant difference between the two bacterial groups before exposure to nano zinc and after exposure to nano zinc. A 1.6-fold increase in *norA* gene expression and a 0.8-fold increase in *norB* gene expression were observed (Figure 9).

Figure 9. The result of 12 resistant isolates, before and after exposure to the nano zinc.

Furthermore, the Real-time PCR results before and after exposure to both nano zinc and sub-MIC CP were examined which showed a 1.4-fold increase in norA gene expression and a 0.4-fold increase in norB gene expression (Figure 10).

Figure 10. The result of 12 resistant isolates, before and after exposure to the both nano zinc and sub-MIC CP.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

One of the most dangerous and ancient human infections is *Staphylococcus aureus*, a well-known member of the *Staphylococcus* genus that has been there for more than a century (21). There are more than 20 species of *Staphylococcus* spread over different habitats. Some live in animal mucous membranes, skin glands, and skin, polluting natural waterways, soil, sand, dust, and air as well as animal-derived foods including cheese, milk, and meat (22). *Staphylococcus aureus* primarily colonizes the anterior nares, but it can also be detected in other areas such as injured skin, the axillae, the vagina, the perineum, and the nasopharyngeal mucosa (23).

Staphylococcus aureus is a commonplace bacteria that has a high potential for human pathogenicity due to its abundance of virulence characteristics and ability to withstand harsh environmental conditions. Globally, particularly in Iran, the rise of antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus* strains presents serious challenges to the management of the disease (24). This pathogen is a global leader in hospital- and community-acquired infections, and it plays a role in a variety of illnesses including endocarditis, wound infections, septicemia, and bacteremia (25).

The management of microbiological infections is consistently hampered by the treatment of staphylococcal infections, which is one of the biggest threats posed by antibiotic resistance in the twenty-first

century. Because *Staphylococcus aureus* is prone to developing emergent antibiotic resistance, it is especially important to control hospital infections (26).

Staphylococcus aureus exhibits modulation of antibiotic resistance through both chromosomal and plasmid-encoded pathways (27). Prolonged and indiscriminate antibiotic usage fosters a surge in resistance and a decline in bacterial susceptibility to various antibiotic classes (28). The transmission of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains among individuals increases the likelihood of spreading the infection throughout populations. These isolates impart resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics, aminoglycosides, and macrolides simultaneously, and are distinguished by their multidrug resistance (29).

In medical practice, fluoroquinolones are a class of broad-spectrum antibiotics that are frequently used as an oral substitute for gastrointestinal absorption. Mutations in the norA and norB genes are common triggers for efflux pump activity, which frequently results in resistance to fluoroquinolones (30). Antibiotics like ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin are successfully extruded by these pumps, which causes resistance to these drugs (31).

The NorA and NorB efflux pumps are prominent members of the Major Facilitator Superfamily (MFS) efflux system, which is a crucial efflux mechanism in the *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterium. A substantial body

of research highlights their function in eliminating a variety of substances, including ethidium bromide, tetravalent ammonium compounds, and fluoroquinolones like norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin (32, 33). Notably, resistance to antibiotic drugs is produced by basal expression of the *norA* gene within the cell. Elevated expression of the *NorA* efflux pump is correlated with enhanced resistance to fluoroquinolones (34). Similarly, research highlights the role of the *NorB* efflux pump in increasing the pathogenicity of this bacteria and its ability to withstand biocides and fluoroquinolone antibiotics (35).

During the first stage of this study, we evaluated each isolated strain's resistance to the fluoroquinolone antibiotics of ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin, ofloxacin, and levofloxacin. Fifty of the 88 strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* that were analyzed showed resistance to ciprofloxacin (56.81%), indicating a rising trend in resistance to fluoroquinolones. These results are consistent with a 2013 study by Neeta D et al. in India, which found that ciprofloxacin resistance was common at 57.6%, ofloxacin resistance at 51.2%, and levofloxacin resistance at 30.4% (36). Notably, MRSA strains have become more resistant to quinolones in recent years (37). Among Iranian research, Saadat et al.'s 2014 investigation is noteworthy because it found that just 4.7% of patients had ciprofloxacin resistance (38). Furthermore, isolates obtained from Imam Reza Hospital in Mashhad between 2013 and 2015 showed a 13.4% resistance rate to ciprofloxacin, according to a 2016 study by Tabai et al. (39). On the other hand, our research highlights a growing trend of *Staphylococcus aureus* strains becoming resistant to fluoroquinolone drugs.

Few studies have looked into the interaction of efflux pumps with zinc nanoparticles and medication effects like ciprofloxacin on strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* in Iran. Using accurate, molecular, and quantitative Real-Time PCR techniques, the goal of this work was to determine and modify the expression levels of the *norA* and *norB* genes in the pre-treatment and three treatment stages including zinc and ciprofloxacin. First, isolated isolates were identified by culture and biochemical methods. Next, the definitive Multiplex PCR approach was used for molecular characterization, focusing on two important diagnostic genes, *femA*, and *nuc* (40, 41).

Several investigations have attempted to molecularly identify *Staphylococcus aureus* by utilizing different genes to identify the organism. Among these, *femA* (42-46), *nuc* (47, 48), non-protein coding RNA (*npcRNA*) (49) and *scaF* (50) genes can be mentioned. After a thorough analysis of relevant literature, we determined that *nuc* and *femA* are viable options for *Staphylococcus aureus* detection. All ninety isolates that were validated through biochemical tests were examined using primers that targeted the *femA* and *nuc* genes through the use of the Multiplex PCR technique. Later, it was determined that 88 (97%) of the isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus*; of them, 83 (94.31%) had the *femA* gene and 85 (96.59%) carried the *nuc* gene. Notably, both genes were present in 80 (90.9%) isolates.

The *mecA* gene is useful for detecting methicillin resistance, while the *femA* and *nuc* genes are useful for identifying *S. aureus*, according to several studies. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) isolates carrying the *mecA* and *femA* genes have been shown to exhibit strong phenotypic concordance with genotypic testing (40, 51). Furthermore, studies have demonstrated the 100% sensitivity of the

heat-resistant *nuc* gene in detecting isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* (41, 52).

In the study by Kobayashi et al., the *mecA* gene was found in 100% of the isolates of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and 16.7% of the isolates of methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA). PCR analysis revealed that 10.6% of the *S. aureus* isolates did not show any *femA* gene products. Our study's results for the molecular diagnosis of *Staphylococcus aureus* are 89.4% better than those of Kobayashi (43) and 71.4% better than those of A. Breves et al. (53). This improvement can be ascribed to the simultaneous use of two critical diagnostic genes, *nuc*, and *femA*, through the Multiplex PCR method. Notably, Kobayashi and A. Breves, who only used the *femA* gene for molecular identification, were unable to identify *Staphylococcus aureus* strains with 100% specificity, most likely as a result of gene heterogeneity between strains (54). On the other hand, R. Sahebnaasagh et al.'s study (55), which only used the *nuc* gene for molecular diagnosis (80.15%) performed better than our study's results (97%), suggesting that the *nuc* gene is a more efficient method for molecular diagnosis than multiplex PCR and simultaneous use of multiple diagnostic genes.

Efflux pump phenotypic and genotypic identification in *Staphylococcus aureus* strains has been the subject of numerous studies. In the present investigation, we sought to evaluate the resistance to zinc nanoparticles alone, in combination with ciprofloxacin, and relation to the activity of *NorA* and *NorB* efflux pumps. Using multiplex PCR, the Cardwell test, and the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of ciprofloxacin in the presence of Carbonyl cyanide *m*-chlorophenyl hydrazone (CCCP) efflux pump inhibitor, we first screened the isolates for the presence of *norA* and *norB* genes and their functionality with the specified compounds. The Real-Time PCR method was then utilized to evaluate these genes' expression changes.

Twelve isolates with phenotypically active efflux pumps were found among the fifty resistant samples found using the disk diffusion method. This was verified by the Sub MIC CP test using CCCP at a 10 μ M concentration. As resistant isolates, isolates were chosen that showed a drop in ciprofloxacin MIC in the presence of CCCP. This group of isolates was used to assess the effects of nanoparticles both alone and in conjunction with ciprofloxacin, as well as a standard strain of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923) possessing active pumps.

The existence of the *norA* and *norB* genes was evaluated in all resistance strains after the isolation of resistant isolates, and the Multiplex PCR technique was used to validate the presence of these genes. Using the Real-Time PCR technique, Pourmand et al. (2014) investigated the expression of the efflux pump gene *norA* in ciprofloxacin-resistant bacteria. According to their research, all ciprofloxacin-resistant strains had the *norA* gene, and the presence of hexahydroquinolone biocide increased the gene's expression (50).

Huet et al. studied the expression and existence of efflux pumps in nine ciprofloxacin-resistant methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) strains in 2008. These genes were first identified, and then their expression levels in the presence of modest quantities of biocides were investigated. The results of the investigation showed that all strains had *NorA* and *NorB* efflux pumps and that the presence of biocides increased the expression of these pumps (56).

In order to study the effect of NorA and NorB pumps on fluoroquinolone antibiotic resistance, we looked at 12 resistant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923) as well as one standard strain sample in four distinct treatment stages. Pre-treatment circumstances as well as three different treatment conditions were included in these states: ciprofloxacin therapy alone, zinc nanoparticle treatment, and sub-minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of ciprofloxacin combined with zinc nanoparticle treatment. Real-time polymerase chain reaction was used to do both quantitative and qualitative assessments of gene expression (PCR). To make sure the PCR reactions were accurate, two reference genes—16S rRNA and *jmK*—were used.

Following the molecular confirmation of the strains and verification of the presence of the main and reference genes under study, we investigated the potential roles of *norA* and *norB* genes and their correlation with resistance to fluoroquinolones in two distinct groups: before treatment with antibiotics and zinc nanoparticles, and after treatment with these compounds.

Therefore, in order to accurately and quantitatively evaluate the expression levels, the Real-Time PCR technique was used. The isolates were exposed to the antibiotic ciprofloxacin, and the results of the Real-Time PCR study showed that there was an average overexpression of the *norA* gene by 1.5 times and the *norB* gene by 2.3 fold. On the other hand, subjecting the *norA* and *norB* genes to a concentration of 1024 mg/ml of zinc nanoparticles caused an average upregulation of 1.6 and 0.8 times, respectively. Notably, the *norA* gene's expression increased by 1.4 fold while the *norB* gene's expression increased by 0.4 fold in the Sub MIC CP with zinc nanoparticles.

The expression levels and overexpression of genes linked to fluoroquinolone (ciprofloxacin) resistance in isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* were examined in a study conducted by Carmen E. DeMarco et al. Higher expression levels of *mepA* (4.4%), *mdeA* (11.4%), *norA* (22.8%), *norB* (25.4%), and *norC* (16.7%) were found in the study (57).

Using ethidium bromide, Patel et al. (2010) examined the efflux pump activity in strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Their results showed that this approach had a 92% specificity for identifying efflux pump activity, which was associated with the expression of the *norA* gene (58). Similarly, using ethidium bromide, Costa et al. (2013) investigated efflux pumps in 50 bacteria resistant to ciprofloxacin. Their research showed how important efflux pumps are in reducing antibiotic and biocide resistance (59). Based on a comparison of these findings with our research, it appears that the *norA* and *norB* genes are present in the majority of strains that are resistant to ciprofloxacin, which may be a factor in *Staphylococcus aureus*'s resistance to the antibiotic. On the other hand, alternative processes such as drug inactivation and target site change, in addition to other efflux pumps, may be involved in conferring ciprofloxacin resistance in bacteria that lack these genes but nevertheless display resistance to the antibiotic.

First, when ciprofloxacin exposure was compared to all other situations and to the *norA* gene, the expression of the *norB* gene increased considerably. This was revealed by comparing the results obtained from the various conditions tested in this study. These results are consistent with research by Que Chi Truong-Bolduc et al. from 2005 to 2012, which assessed the effects of pH and aeration on the overexpression of *norB* and *norA* genes in *Staphylococcus aureus* when fluoroquinolone drugs were present. The higher expression of these genes indicates that the antibiotic is being effluxed more effectively, which could result in strains with active pumps being more resistant. Consequently, strains possessing active pumps are anticipated to become progressively more resistant to fluoroquinolone compounds over time, owing to the heightened efficacy of their efflux pumps.

When ciprofloxacin was added to nanoparticles, the conditions under investigation showed a smaller rise in expression than when nanoparticles were treated alone. This implies that the co-administration of ciprofloxacin and nanoparticles may reduce the overexpression of the efflux pumps *NorA* and *NorB*, preventing the overabundance of pumps and the emergence of resistance. The 2010 study by Roy et al., which looked at the phenotypic impact of zinc nanoparticles (at a concentration of 100 µg/disc) in combination with several antibiotics on strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, supports this conclusion. The investigation found that giving zinc nanoparticles and antibiotics at the same time increased the sensitivity of *Staphylococcus aureus* strains, causing the diameter of inhibition zones to expand by 2 to 10 mm (60). The results obtained in our study confirmed the results obtained in the study of Roy et al. in terms of phenotypic.

Conclusion

The results of our investigation suggest that applying zinc nanoparticles and the antibiotic ciprofloxacin at the same time may prevent the expression of pump genes linked to bacterial resistance to fluoroquinolone drugs. As a result, using these substances is suggested as a possible tactic for managing or avoiding bacterial resistance. To determine whether it would be feasible to use these substances in place of or in addition to antibiotics, more research is necessary. Furthermore, comparison analyses with different antibiotics under different situations should be taken into account. To create nanoparticles of the highest purity and maximize desired results while limiting nanoparticle concentration requirements, a variety of nanoparticle synthesis techniques should be investigated.

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Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

5. References

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